

POSSIBILITIES OF USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS: THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article presents an opinion on the introduction of information and communication tools, on the methods and features of its application, as well as the forms and mechanisms of its application in the courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular in the legislation and practice that regulate the activities of civil and economic courts. In particular, recommendations are presented on improving the procedural order related to applying to the court, accepting applications, distributing them, considering cases on the merits, sending judicial acts to the Bureau of Compulsory Enforcement in the activities of courts in the process preceding the stage of issuing final judicial acts. At the same time, recommendations are presented on the legal status of persons participating in procedural legal relations, and the possibilities and restrictions on the use of information and communication tools.

Key words: court, judge, assistant judge, videoconference, electronic appeal, electronic distribution, remote consideration of cases

Until now, in the activities of the courts of the republic, the following practice has existed and is effectively used for the introduction of information and communication technologies in the activities of courts, including remote appeal to courts, participation in court hearings using a videoconferencing system, automatic distribution of cases between judges, publication of court decisions in Internet, electronic submission of enforcement documents to the Compulsory Enforcement Bureau and significant results obtained from such procedures when considering civil cases in inter-district, district, city courts of first instance.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to digitalize the activities of the judiciary” dated 03.09.2020 No. PP-4818 creates certain conditions not only for citizens, but also for judges and court employees, and also establishes the priority of observing procedural discipline in the judicial system.

At present, an opportunity has been provided for the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies in the

activities of courts, the establishment of electronic relations in this system, and most importantly, the definition and strengthening of the legal foundations for the digitalization of the activities of courts.

Relevance of the topic. In the context of the reforms of New Uzbekistan, the practice of remote legal proceedings is expanding in order to create additional conditions for judicial activities and the population in the field of legal proceedings. Important in this area is the correct and efficient use of information and communication tools and their application. In particular, this process has created more favorable opportunities in the context of the pandemic, which is caused by the conduct of court hearings remotely in remote and nearby areas and the presence of great efficiency in the resolution of cases. In a pandemic, as a result of using this method, it was possible to solve problems quickly and in a timely manner, including the protection of public health. Remote resolution of procedural issues was considered a necessary tool for familiarizing with the case materials, assisting in the consideration of the case, fulfilling court orders, securing a claim, securing evidence, obtaining explanations from the parties, obtaining testimonies and using other means of proof in the case. In Uzbekistan, scientific research in the field of the use of information and communication technologies is not enough, in particular, relations in the field of video conferencing are being strengthened, but there are few scientific works in this area.

A court session in the videoconferencing mode means a remote court session through interactive interaction between the court considering the case and the court assisting in the conduct of the court session, using the possibility of exchanging audio and video information using telecommunication technologies in real time.

The court hearing the case means the court in which the relevant proceeding is located. A court facilitating a court session via videoconferencing means a court of the Republic of Uzbekistan that is outside the jurisdiction of the court considering the case and provides technical and other conditions for holding a court session via videoconferencing.

Courts should pay attention to the fact that the participation of persons participating in the case and other participants in economic proceedings in the court session via videoconferencing is their right, not their obligation.

All persons participating in the case have the right to petition the court to participate in the court session via videoconferencing, being within the same

administrative-territorial unit (Republic of Karakalpakstan, region, city of Tashkent, district, city), i.e. in the territory, where the economic court considering the case is located, but from the building of another court. Grounds for the emergence of videoconferencing technologies in civil proceedings:

Improving legislation in the field of ICT in 2013-2014, creating favorable conditions for citizens, increasing.

Purpose of video conferencing :

- wide introduction of modern technologies in the activity of courts;
- creation of a mechanism aimed at harmonization in accordance with modern requirements and international standards;
- subjects are given freedom to apply to the court;
- digitalization of court activities;
- ensuring openness, publicity and transparency in the activities of the courts;
- data exchange between ministries and departments;
- saving time;
- avoiding unnecessary expenses;
- Strengthening public control over the activities of the courts;
- creating the possibility of remote appeal to the courts;
- creation of favorable conditions for holding a court session remotely;
- strengthens cooperation between courts in different regions;
- simplification of the procedure for considering a case in court;
- the emergence of an opportunity to send letters of request to other courts or a reduction in the implementation of such actions;
- preventing the impossibility to appear at the court session.

According to statistics, the total number of cases considered in the courts of the republic (using the example of civil courts) for 3 months of 2021 is 438 cases, the number of court hearings - 538, the number of persons providing assistance in court - 1426, 669 871 249 million sum saved, the number of persons who assisted in the consideration of cases is 572.

However, studies on which regions were the most conducted, which categories of cases and which subjects were involved, were not conducted.

Benefits of video conferencing:

- Creates favorable conditions for the population when applying to the court and considering cases, especially in a pandemic;
- Improves the online work system (remotely);

- Contributes to the strengthening of technological capabilities for digitalization in litigation;
- Increases efficiency in court proceedings, ensures strict observance of procedural deadlines;
- Reduces the cost of using paper media in litigation;
- Prevents process participants from wasting their time excessively ;
- Ensures openness and transparency in litigation;
- Creates a favorable opportunity for the introduction of videoconferencing in office work.

Environmental impact of videoconferencing :

- Contributes to the protection of public health, creates favorable conditions for the human factor;
- Facilitates improved circulation and online communication during the pandemic;
- Limits the spread of disease during pandemics;
- Prevents environmental pollution;
- Reduces paper consumption and environmental impact;
- Increases energy efficiency.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. The category of cases considered by videoconferencing is not specifically provided. The EPC stipulates that the videoconferencing regime applies to all cases, except for cases that are considered in a closed court session. For example, in family disputes in which one of the parties is outside the relevant jurisdiction, proceedings in this mode are allowed:

if one of the parties is in remote areas,

if one of the parties is being treated in a hospital,

if one of the parties is doing military service,

if one of the parties is in penitentiaries.

2. In order to ensure the possibility of online monitoring of the trial by interested persons, not only videoconferencing within the framework of the court's activities, but also the use of other publicly available means of information and communication technologies outside the Supreme Court system is allowed;

3. Develop a mobile application that allows you to take part in court hearings via videoconferencing, and cover its implementation in full practice. At the moment we cannot say 100%.

4. According to the Civil Procedure Code, a protocol is kept on cases, but in the norm of the Civil Procedure Code regarding rights and obligations, as well as (familiarization with the protocols (audio protocols) of court sessions, other materials of the court case;) Chapter 25. Court protocol. (Art. 276, 277 Code of Civil Procedure).

5. Persons responsible for organizing the videoconferencing and "persons responsible for the technical support of the videoconferencing" are indicated in the ruling and decision of the court and the minutes of the court session. Taking into account the fact that the Code of Civil Procedure does not provide for such categories of subjects participating in the case, their status, rights and obligations and responsibilities should be indicated. Art. 54 Code of Civil Procedure.

6. Implementation of inter-sectoral and various inter-regional video conferences, for example, with the participation of third parties, accomplices, etc.

7. New scientific terms appear in the video conferencing mode. In order to systematically ensure the fulfillment of the tasks specified in this Decree, the following opinions are put forward:

- Inclusion in the range of topics indicated in the research programs, such topics as "Conceptual issues for the implementation of information and communication technologies in the activities of the courts", "Digitalization of the court activity: substantive and procedural aspects", "Judicial activity and automation system" and conducting research in these topics contributes to the effectiveness of scientific and technical achievements;
- It is necessary to create conditions for judges to work remotely and develop the legal framework, and most importantly, expand the material and technical capabilities of the courts, in particular, it is advisable to create a "Virtual Room".

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